

Augmenting controls for tracked vehicles with force and tactile feedback: a work in progress

Thomas Howard, Benjamin Geslot, and Jérôme Perret

Haption S.A.S, Soulge-sur-Ouette, France

Corresponding author: thomas.howard@haption.com

Keywords: Haptics, Force Feedback, Vibrotactile Feedback, Off-Highway Vehicles

Motivation

The THEIA^{XR} project (TheiaXR, 2024) is concerned with integrating novel human-machine interaction (HMI) technologies in off-highway vehicles, in order to improve operation safety, efficiency and operators' quality of work. In the off-highway vehicle domain, many vehicles move using tracks rather than wheels, as this allows better stability and traction on soft and loose ground such as e.g., sand, mud or snow (Wong, 1997). Such tracked vehicles are operated using a pair of levers which allow the operator to independently set the velocity setpoint for each track, allowing agile maneuvering on complex terrain (see Figure P 34). Existing track controls exclusively act as input devices for the operator, and provide no form of assistance to the user or feedback on the current status of the operated machine.

The provision of haptic feedback has been extensively studied in wheeled road vehicles (Gaffary and Lécuyer, 2018) and their simulators (Petermeijer et al., 2015). Force feedback through the steering wheel has been shown to be effective for e.g., steering assistance and vehicle targeting (Dennerlein et al., 2000, lane-keeping (Prinoth, 2024), and the safe maneuvering of vehicles with attached trailers (Morales et al., 2013). Tactile feedback on the other hand has been shown to effectively assist vehicle navigation (Hwang and Ryu, 2010), obstacle avoidance [1] and speed control (Birrell et al., 2013). Force feedback has also been explored for teleoperated tracked robots and vehicles [5], but has never been applied within a tracked vehicle cabin in a drive-by-wire context.

In this work, we therefore seek to investigate potential benefits that could be obtained by turning track controls into haptic feedback devices capable of delivering dual force and tactile feedback to an operator located directly inside the vehicle cabin.

Acknowledgements

This work has been funded by the European Union within the Horizon Europe Framework under Grant Agreement No. 101092861 (Research and Innovation Action "THEIA-XR"). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure P 34. Examples of tracked off-highway vehicles studied within the THEIAXR project (left) with examples of associated track control levers (circled in red, right)

Device prototype

We designed a prototype (see Figure P 35) substitute for a pair of track control levers of a Prinoth Leitwolf snowgroomer [9].

Figure P 35. (Left) CAD design of the first prototype, showing the vibrotactile actuators integrated into the handles and the DC motors providing independent torque feedback to each lever. (Right) Assembled prototype.

The prototype features a pair of symmetrically arranged levers rotating a shaft whose angular position is measured using a Maxon MR 1000 point relative encoder, while torque feedback can be

independently provided on each shaft through an attached Maxon RE25 DC motor coupled with a HFUC-2A Harmonic Drive strain wave gear reductor with a ratio of 50. We integrated Titan Haptics TacHammer Carlton linear magnetic ram actuators capable of delivering intense high-fidelity vibrotactile feedback cues within the tip of each lever. The vibrotactile actuators are driven using custom-built electronics based on an Arduino Micro and a pair of Texas Instruments DRV2605 haptic drivers, connected to the main embedded controller via SPI. Force feedback control is achieved using a proprietary embedded controller designed by Haption, communicating with a host software on a PC via EtherCAT. This host software is e.g. capable of interfacing the haptic track controls with a simulated snowgroomer and environment in Unity3D.

Envisioned haptic assistance functions and future work

In upcoming evaluation work, we will integrate the designed prototype into a realistic snowgrooming simulator environment in order to test the acceptability and effectiveness of the haptic assistance functions detailed below.

We will investigate the impact of tactile feedback on improving lane-keeping during snowgrooming, e.g., to ensure consistent overlap and parallelism between passes on groomed ski slopes (see Figure P 36 left). Velocity has a significant impact on resulting snow quality, we will also investigate the use of tactile warnings in case of excessive velocity. Also, significant discrepancies between the commanded track velocities and the vehicle ground velocity measured e.g., using GPS, may be an indicator of the vehicle treading in place, digging itself into a pit and damaging the groomed snow slope. We will therefore investigate tactile warnings relating to excessive or insufficient vehicle velocity (see Figure P 36 center). Finally, we plan to assess whether tactile warnings of impending collisions can assist the operator in quickly reacting to avoid them (see Figure P 36 right).

Figure P 36. Concepts for tactile feedback assistance for navigation (left), speed control (center) and obstacle avoidance (right)

Regarding the use of force-feedback capabilities, we will investigate the idea of guiding the user towards a lower velocity as a complementary form of feedback to the tactile velocity warnings mentioned above. Furthermore, we are in the process of implementing a navigation assistance controller, which gently guides the operator towards the ideal track control lever pose required to reach a defined vehicle orientation and velocity (see Figure P 37).

Figure P 37. Concept for torque feedback navigation assistance

References

- Ahtamad, M., Gray, R., Ho, C., Reed, N., & Spence, C. (2015). Informative collision warnings: effect of modality and driver age. in Proceedings of the 8th International Driving Symposium on Human Factors in Driver Assessment, Training and Vehicle Design (Salt Lake City, Utah), 330–336. <https://doi.org/10.17077/drivingassessment.1590>
- Birrell, S. A., Young, M. S., & Weldon, A. M. (2013). Vibrotactile pedals: provision of haptic feedback to support economical driving. *Ergonomics* 56, 282–292. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00140139.2012.760750>
- Dennerlein, J. T., Martin, D. B., & Hasser, C. (2000). Force-feedback improves performance for steering and combined steering-targeting tasks. In Proceedings of the SIGCHI conference on Human factors in computing systems (pp. 423–429).
- Gaffary, Y., & Lécuyer, A. (2018). The use of haptic and tactile information in the car to improve driving safety: A review of current technologies. *Frontiers in ICT*, 5, 5. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fict.2018.00005>
- Horan, B., Creighton, D., Nahavandi, S., & Jamshidi, M. (2007). Bilateral haptic teleoperation of an articulated track mobile robot. In 2007 IEEE International Conference on System of Systems Engineering (pp. 1–8).
- Hwang, S., & Ryu, J. H. (2010). The Haptic steering Wheel: Vibro-tactile based navigation for the driving environment. In 2010 8th IEEE PERCOM Workshops (pp. 660–665).
- Morales, J., Mandow, A., Martínez, J. L., Reina, A. J., & García-Cerezo, A. (2013). Driver assistance system for passive multi-trailer vehicles with haptic steering limitations on the leading unit. *Sensors*, 13(4), 4485–4498. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s130404485>
- Petermeijer, S. M., Abbink, D. A., Mulder, M., & De Winter, J. C. (2015). The effect of haptic support systems on driver performance: A literature survey. *IEEE transactions on haptics*, 8(4), 467–479.
- Prinoth A.G. (2024), <https://www.prinoth-snowgroomers.com/en/products/leitwolf>
- Switkes, J. P. (2005). Handwheel Force Feedback With Lanekeeping Assistance: Combined Dynamics, Stability and Bounding, a dissertation of doctor of philosophy.
- THEIAXR (2024). <https://www.theia-xr.eu/>
- Wong, J. Y. (1997). Dynamics of tracked vehicles. *Vehicle system dynamics*, 28(2–3), 197–219. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00423119708969354>